

Adventitia Segmentation On Superficial Femoral Artery Optical Coherence Tomography Images

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Abstract—Atherosclerotic disease on peripheral arteries, commonly known as peripheral artery disease represents accumulation of cholesterol in peripheral arteries. It causes the formation of different types of depositions called plaques which cause thickening of the arterial walls resulting in reduced blood flow to lower extremities, in case of femoral arteries, upper extremities, in case of brachial artery or brain in case of carotid artery. Current research shows that approximately 8.5 million Americans, aged over 40 years, are affected by peripheral artery disease while one fourth of them falls into a severe category. For these reasons, an early detection of the disease is important. In order to detect the disease, arteries need to be imaged properly. In the recent years, an increase of optical coherence imaging has occurred due to the ease of use and the ability to detect tissue morphology which is extremely important for the detection of the disease. From the tissue morphology, it is of most importance to observe the tissue between lumen and intimal layer of the artery, since the majority of the plaques form in that region, but it is also important to observe the region between intima and adventitia (the outer wall of the artery) since the plaque can penetrate the intimal layer as well. In this paper, a deterministic approach for the detection of the adventitia is described based on the previously detected intimal layer of the artery. The proposed method is evaluated on optical coherence tomography images from 8 specimens of porcine femoral arteries. The results show that the detection of adventitia is possible on this image modality with Dice coefficient 0.9805 and Hausdorff distance 0.1 mm.

Index Terms—segmentation, peripheral artery, optical coherence tomography.

I. INTRODUCTION

Peripheral artery disease (PAD) is a chronic and progressive atherosclerotic disease causing the formation of depositions

called plaques that lead to total or partial occlusion of the arteries. PAD typically include the atherosclerosis of abdominal aorta, iliac arteries, femoral and other lower limb arteries and, infrequently, the upper extremities [1]. It commonly includes various diseases that affect nonintracranial and noncardiac arteries [2]. Peripheral artery disease affects nearly 200 million people in the world and 8.5 million in the USA [3], [4].

Imaging is the most accurate diagnostic modality for atherosclerosis and imaging modalities used depend on the availability and the suspected diagnosis. In terms of PAD, most commonly used imaging modalities are duplex ultrasound, computed tomography angiography and magnetic resonance angiography [5]. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) is a common imaging modality in vascular medicine as it has emerged as powerful due to its ability to provide high-resolution cross-sectional images of arterial structures. OCT is particularly advantageous in the context of arterial imaging due to its ability to provide detailed visualization of the arterial wall layers, including the lumen and intima [6]. This level of detail is crucial for the accurate assessment of atherosclerotic plaque composition, plaque growth, and atherosclerosis staging, which is a key factor in determining progression of PAD and the risk of subsequent cardiovascular events [6].

OCT images are quantitatively analysed in order to segment the artery into the lumen and the arterial wall into its constituent layers, tunica intima, tunica media and tunica adventitia. Upon accurate segmentation, arterial wall thickness can be determined, allowing for the assessment of plaque burden and identification of vulnerable plaques prone to rupture. However, the presence of anatomically complex atherosclerotic lesions in PAD makes segmentation of the diseased arterial wall difficult because the normal arterial

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architecture is distorted. Furthermore, due to the dynamic nature of atherosclerotic plaque development, characterized by processes such as calcification, lipid accumulation, and neovascularization, an additional layer of complexity to the segmentation task is added [7]. Despite these challenges, accurate segmentation must be done to properly evaluate the disease and to enable guidance of therapeutic interventions, such as angioplasty or stenting, which aim to restore adequate blood flow to affected regions [7].

Conventional methods of segmentation have relied heavily on manual delineation by experts, which is both time-consuming and more importantly, subject to inter-observer variability. However, advancements in technology, mainly artificial intelligence and machine learning have led to the development of automated and semi-automated segmentation algorithms, which have shown promising results in enhancing the accuracy and reproducibility of OCT image analysis [8].

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the development of deep learning-based approaches for the segmentation of OCT images derived from atherosclerosis diagnostics and they have demonstrated superior performance compared to traditional techniques. These approaches rely on leveraging large datasets of images annotated by physicians to train neural networks capable of recognizing subtle distinct features within the arterial wall that are indicative of specific tissue types [9]. A fully automated tissue classification method for coronary artery classification was proposed by Abdolmanafi et al. [10]. They have used a pre-trained CNN as feature extractor for removing the classification layers and subsequently the activations of the last fully connected layer to train Random Forest and support vector machine algorithms. The sensitivity of the algorithms was 0.97, 0.95 and 0.87, respectively [10]. Lee et al., have designed a convolutional neural network for automatic microchannel detection and achieved a Dice coefficient 0.92 [11]. In the work by Zahnd et al., a CNN for automatic segmentation based on contours of arterial wall layers was developed and the system has achieved a Dice coefficient 0.93 [12]. A novel level set based lumen segmentation method was proposed for IVOCT images by Cao et al., [13] to solve the problem of irregular lumen. The experimental results showed that the proposed method is robust with an average Dice score 0.98 [13].

Current state-of-the-art methods for arterial segmentation fall short of providing a comprehensive tool for arterial segmentation. Given the significant clinical burden of PAD, the importance of accurate and timely diagnosis, and the inherent challenges associated with manual quantification of OCT images, developing a robust algorithm for comprehensive segmentation is crucial. In this work, we propose a novel algorithm for segmentation of the artery into the arterial lumen and the distinct arterial wall layers, tunica intima, tunica media, and tunica adventitia.

In our most recent efforts [14], [15], we established the possibility of segmenting lumen and intima from OCT images in coronary and femoral arteries. There, multiple different convolutional neural networks were used for the task. However, as

already established, an automatic, deep learning segmentation of the outer wall of the artery is extremely hard. We also explained the necessity of the intima segmentation for the detection of atherosclerosis and further the need for segmenting adventitia. Here, we aim to automatically segment the outer wall of the artery through deterministic methods and based on theoretical parameters. Results are evaluated from the aspect of Dice coefficient and Hausdorff distance.

The remainder of our paper encompasses five sections. In Section II, the methodology for the segmentation of adventitia is proposed. Section III provides additional information about the dataset and describes the experimental setup. In Section IV we present the achieved results and compare them in terms of Dice coefficient and Hausdorff distance. Section V concludes our study and we discuss the drawbacks of our approach and provide suggestions for the future work.

II. METHODOLOGY FOR IMAGE SEGMENTATION

In order to solve the problem of the 3D reconstruction of femoral arteries from OCT images, in our previous work, we have used convolutional neural networks for the task of segmenting lumen and intimal layer of the artery first from coronary and later from femoral arteries [14], [15]. There, we established the possibility for the automatic extraction of the intimal layer and its necessity for the 3D reconstruction. Because of the limits of OCT technology and user error, it is hard to observe adventitia on the images, especially on diseased patients. Example of differences in the location of arterial tissue layers is given in Fig. 1. As it can be seen, intima layer on the diseased artery can stretch to the border of the region of interest (ROI). This means that, in some regions, adventitia, or parts of it, have not been imaged properly. This makes it extremely difficult to accurately segment adventitia. In addition to this, a clear border of adventitia, in the majority of cases and even in the cases with extremely good penetration, cannot be clearly seen by the specialist thus making it difficult to collect a dataset for the purposes of training AI models. For these reasons, a deterministic approach is the only viable solution. Similar to [16], we use thicknesses of the arterial layers to properly outline the adventitia. As concluded in the most recent studies [17], [18], the average diameter of healthy human femoral arteries averages in 8.5 mm in adults while intima-media thickness (IMT) is ranging from 0.53 - 0.73 [19], [20]. In addition, IMT increases with age for approximately 0.003 mm per year [19]. Since the majority of plaques is located in the intima-media region [21], (the region between intima-media border and outer wall of the artery does not change in thickness) and the fact that it is mostly asymmetrical [22], [23], the approach by [16] is insufficient since the majority of the plaques was symmetrical. This means that lumen expansion in the case of asymmetrical plaque deposits would lead to inaccuracies. In order to accustom to that, we suggest the expansion of intimal layer instead of lumen layer. This, small adjustment, adjusts for the asymmetrical nature of the plaque compositions. Since the overall thickness of the arterial wall ranges from 1 - 2 mm [24], [25], and previously

Fig. 1. Healthy (left) and diseased (right) artery example with intima annotation.

Fig. 2. Difference between lumen (green) and intima (blue) expansion.

stated IMT ranging from 0.53 - 0.73, we selected 0.84 mm as the value for which the intimal region would be expanded. The difference between lumen and intima expansion can be observed in Fig. 2. While the difference is between adventitia regions on diseased artery is not significant, the error of the lumen expansion can be observed based on the distance between intima and alleged adventitia border where the distance is only a few pixels in some regions. These inaccuracies can lead to large differences when we proceed to 3D reconstruction and even more in the case of fluid dynamics.

The expansion can be achieved in two different ways: image processing and point cloud (metric space) processing. In the case of image processing a simple matrix multiplication is the best solution. In order to do so, image with intima extracted should be multiplied by disk matrix with the size of 47 where the value range is 0.1. Since the computational cost of such multiplication is high, knowing that the matrix size would be 95x95, an iterative approach is used. Instead of doing one multiplication with the disk matrix with the size 47, size 5 disc matrix is iterated 8 times and the size 7 disc matrix is iterated one time. An example of size 3 disc matrix is given in (1).

Unlike the image approach, the point cloud approach boils down to the transformation of the intima contours into the metric space, calculation of the geometrical center of the contour and movement of the contour so that the geometrical center would be in the coordinates (0,0) in the Cartesian coordinate system. This is done in order to simplify the calculations. After the movement, the points of intima contour are moved radially by 0.84 mm. In order to move the coordinates, a distance between a geometrical center and point in the intima contour as represented in (2). This is done in order to calculate the distance ratio between that calculated distance d and the desired distance dt as represented in (3). Afterwards, the new coordinates are calculated by (4).

Since the coordinates of the geometrical center are $x_0 = 0$ and $y_0 = 0$ (4) is simplified to (5). The main difference between the results of the two methodologies is the computational power needed to do the calculation.

Evaluation of the results in the case of adventitia is hard in this case. With the lack of manually annotated data and any other techniques, the only possible way to evaluate the

results in the calculation of Dice coefficient and the Hausdorff distance [15]. Dice coefficient is defined as two times the area of the intersection of A and B, divided by the sum of the areas A and B. This is represented by (6) where TP is the number of true positives, FP is the number of false positives and FN is the number of false negatives.

The 95th percentile Hausdorff distance is a distance metric that measures the maximum of the minimum distances between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth at the 95th percentile. This metric is used because the Dice coefficient is not sensitive to local differences [26]. The Hausdorff distance between two sets of points X and Y is shown in Fig. 3.

In addition to the mentioned comparison, three more methodologies are used to evaluate the experimental results. Typically, for the task of segmentation, even in medical field, a thresholding technique is used [27], [28]. This is usually done through the manual selection of the thresholding value. The most commonly used thresholding algorithm is Otsu threshold [29].

$$matrix = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

$$d = \sqrt{[(x_1 - x_0)^2 + (y_1 - y_0)^2]}. \quad (2)$$

$$t = dt/d. \quad (3)$$

$$xt = (1 - t)x_0 + tx_1, yt = (1 - t)y_0 + ty_1. \quad (4)$$

$$xt = tx_1, yt = ty_1. \quad (5)$$

$$Dice = 2TP/(2TP + FP + FN). \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. An illustration of Hausdorff distance between two sets of points X and Y [26].

However, thresholding has its limitations. In addition to the computational power needed to produce the best results, it is a manual method and completely relies on the homogeneous nature of the data. In the case of a large amount of artefacts, it would produce a lot of inaccuracies which would lead to poor 3D reconstruction afterwards. In addition, the edges of the segmented surfaces are not the best which requires additional postprocessing.

In comparison to the thresholding method, in the field of medical imaging, active contour techniques are extensively utilized for isolating areas of interest through image segmentation. These contours, which outline the region of interest, are defined by boundaries. Active contours employ energy forces and constraints to segment relevant image pixels [30], [31]. They help in forming smooth, closed boundaries around the region of interest, and include models such as the Snake model, Gradient Vector Flow (GVF), Snake model and geometric contours [30], [31]. The main problem with active contours is the actual definition of the boundaries. In our case, the location of the artery on the image is not consistent, thus, it would be difficult to automatically define the contour or the boundaries.

In order to fix the main problem of the active contour method, we used a conjunction of the thresholding and active contours. Through the thresholding, we are able to find the actual location of the artery, thus, making it easier to apply the active contour model.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Data acquisition and description

A dataset of 300 OCT images of porcine femoral arteries, extracted from 8 porcine specimens, was acquired containing the annotation of intimal region. All of the images were manually annotated by the clinical experts. All of the images have the size of 512x512 pixels with pixel size of 0.01786 x 0.01786 meaning that 1 mm is represented as 56 pixels.

B. Infrastructure

All of the tests have been performed on GIGABYTE NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti GPU with 11 GB of

GDDR5X RAM memory. Python V3.7.13 was used as programming language.

IV. RESULTS

For the task of adventitia generation from OCT images, the method is applied on the previously generated images [15] and compared to the manually annotated intima border adjusted to the size of the adventitia. In addition to the manually annotated data, the method is compared to threshold method, active contour method and the conjunction of two. The results are evaluated from the aspect of Dice coefficient and 95 percentile Hausdorff distance. The experimental results are given in Table I.

As it can be observed, intima expansion achieved overall the best results concerning Dice coefficient and Hausdorff distance. However, in both cases of threshold and active contour methods, the results are comparable. When comparing the Hausdorff distance, the lower is better, and the values of 0.7 and 0.6 would be considered as high for our dataset specially comparing it to 0.1 achieved for the intima expansion.

Even though similar results can be observed from all of the methods when observing healthy arteries in Fig. 4, a larger difference can be observed when processing diseased arteries in Fig. 5. While it can be observed that all of the methods achieved great performance from the aspect of Dice coeff., the same could not be said for Hausdorff distance.

Due to the nature of both threshold and active contour methods, significant data can be lost. While the thresholding

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR ADVENTITIA SEGMENTATION USING DIFFERENT METHODS

Methods	Dice coeff.	Hausdorff distance [mm]
Intima Expansion	0.981	0.1
Otsu Threshold	0.919	0.701
Active contour	0.937	0.623
Otsu + Active contour	0.938	0.489

Fig. 4. Results of the methods for healthy artery: a) source image; b) intima manually annotated expansion; c) threshold detected; d) active contour; e) threshold and active contour combination; f) model output. Green represents detected intima border while blue line represents adventitia border.

Fig. 5. Results of the methods for diseased artery: a) source image; b) intima manually annotated expansion; c) threshold detected; d) active contour; e) threshold and active contour combination; f) model output. Green represents detected intima border while blue line represents adventitia border.

would work better when examining lumen of the artery, due to the high contrast in pixel values, the values near intima border are lower in contrast and the values for adventitia are practically non-existent. This leads to lower Hausdorff distance, the results of which can be observed in Fig. 4 c) and Fig. 5 c) for healthy and diseased arteries. Unlike threshold, the active contours have shown high performance on healthy arteries. When observing diseased arteries the Fig. 5 d), significant errors can be seen which are reflected in poor performance for Hausdorff distance. Similar results can be observed from the combination of two methods in Fig. 4 e) and Fig. 5 e).

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated the possibility of the adventitia identification in intravascular OCT images. We explored different deterministic methods for image segmentation for the purposes of said generation. The methods were applied on the OCT images of the porcine specimens. The methods include intima expansion through the use of anatomic parameters of the arteries. In addition to intima expansion, thresholding and active contour methods were applied and compared with the intima expansion method. All the results were evaluated with Dice coefficient for the global measure and 95th percentile Hausdorff Distance for local differences. Our experiments show high performance of intima expansion method outperforming the other methods.

In contrast to thresholding and active contours method, expansion of intima does not rely on the actual position of the artery on the images nor on their quality while being less computationally expensive. The main drawback of the method is that it does not account for the plaques that could actually form outside the intima layer of the artery. In addition, the manual selection of the thresholding values makes it hard to automatically perform the segmentation.

The identification of the adventitia border is the second stage of the fully automatic 3D reconstruction of the femoral arteries, first being the segmentation of lumen and intima as described in [15]. In the future, a fully automatic 3D reconstruction will be performed which will be visualized employing mixed reality.

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